

ROLE OF FAST RADIOLOGICAL EXAMINATION IN TRAUMA CASES

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Author Details	Abstract
<p>Keywords:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Radiology• Imaging• Trauma• Sonography• Ultrasonography• Emergency management	<p>The rapid screening and evaluation of patients with blunt and penetrating trauma has been made possible with the help of focused assessment with sonography in trauma (FAST) which is a non-invasive and comprehensively employed procedure for acute management of trauma. FAST radiological examination has advanced into more extensive assessment of heart, abdomen, chest and other organs following a trauma in patients who are hemodynamically unstable for the transportation. It has prevented casualties in emergency department of hospitals by timely identification of fluids in pericardium, pleural and peritoneal spaces, also locating fractures, pneumothorax and trauma related organ injuries. FAST radiological examination has reduced the need for invasive course of actions such as exploratory laparotomy and peritoneal lavage and has become the initial imaging tool which helps in critical decision making leading to surgery or any</p>
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other intervention. Being a radiation-free examination that uses ultrasonic waves to diagnose. It is safe for pregnant women and children. The accuracy of this imaging modality depends on the experience and training of the operator. A rapid screening can be done within minutes at the bedside.

INTRODUCTION

The FAST (Focused Assessment with Sonography in Trauma) scan is a non-invasive imaging method used to assess patients in trauma situations. It makes it possible to quickly find free fluid in important places such the pericardial sac, the pelvic region, the colon, the subhepatic space, and beneath the diaphragm. FAST may also be used in some circumstances to detect damage to solid organs.¹ Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST), also referred to as Focused Abdominal Sonography for Trauma, has become a valuable tool. This technique is used to detect pericardial effusion and assess the presence of free fluid within the abdominal and pelvic cavities.²

Trauma remains a leading global cause of death, with over 45 million individuals each year experiencing serious disabilities due to traumatic injuries. One of the most serious of them is chest trauma, particularly in patients who have had several injuries. Chest injuries are responsible for about 25% of trauma-related mortality in those under 40 years old. Penetrating injuries account for only around 10% of thoracic trauma patients, whereas blunt force accounts for the remainder. When assessing patients with acute trauma, chest imaging is crucial. However, it is crucial to choose the best imaging modality for the patient at the right time; mistakes in this process can result in therapy delays, higher expenses, and needless ionizing radiation exposure for patients.

Compared to computed tomography (CT), now considered the most accurate diagnostic tool for pneumothorax, spine chest X-rays have demonstrated a sensitivity as low as 20.9% for detecting this disease.³

The most common cause of traumatic injuries is automobile accidents. Injuries can also result from falls, drowning, burns, sports injuries, violent crimes, and war.⁴

Approximately 20% of patients with major trauma sustain severe abdominal injuries, which carry a mortality rate of around 20%. Penetrating injuries are less frequent in European nations, where blunt trauma accounts for the majority of stomach injuries. The leading cause of death in these situations is still uncontrolled bleeding, which is frequently avoidable, particularly when there is abdominal trauma. Finding free fluid in the abdominal cavity after trauma is the goal of the FAST (Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma) scan. This process can be extended into the E-FAST (Extended FAST) protocol, which can assist in identifying a pneumothorax and evaluate for the presence of fluid in the pleural space.⁵

FAST has been a firstline method for detecting free fluid in patients with abdominal injuries. The pericardial space, Morrison's pouch, perisplenic space, the pouch of Douglas, and the perihepatic space all contain free fluid. FAST was recently expanded to include the right and left pleural spaces as well as two anterior pleural gaps, changing the name to eFAST (extended FAST). A number of modalities are included in radiological imaging, such as (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), ultrasound, and Xrays. Every one of these methods has distinct qualities that affect how they are used in various traumatological situations. Xrays are still one of the most popular modalities and are essential for preliminary evaluations, particularly when it comes to identifying fractures and dislocations. But CT technology's quick developments, such the creation of multislice scanners, have further transformed the diagnostic environment.⁶ The firstline imaging technique for head injury patients who arrive in an emergency room with a neurological impairment is noncontrast CT. Sir Hounsfield introduced the first CT scan, which was a single detector scanner based on Xray technology. Recent developments have led to the development of CT scanners with greater spatial resolution, which can image the entire body in a matter of seconds.⁴ Hepatobiliary and renal abnormalities were the most common, with a frequency of 7.8% for incidental findings on ultrasound in this population, according to a previous study. However, radiologists conducted the FAST evaluations, and if there was no free fluid, solid organ screening ultrasounds were conducted. It has been reported that 1.4% to 27% of incidental computed tomography (CT) findings in trauma settings are reported or followed up on. To our knowledge, there has never been a report on the frequency of incidental discoveries in FAST assessments conducted by emergency physicians. Determining the frequency and kinds of incidental observations found in adult ED trauma patients receiving FAST assessments by emergency doctors was the main objective of this study.⁷

The rationale of using FAST (FOCUSED ASSEMENT WITH SONOGRAPHY IN TRAUMA) scan in radiological trauma cases is to quickly assess for life threatening injuries, particularly hemoperitoneum and hemothorax, in hemodynamically unstable patients. FAST scans are the rapid, bedside ultrasound examination that can help guide initial management, including surgical intervention, without the need of CT scans in unstable patient.

Figure 1: Flow diagram to guide the use of FAST in trauma management in peripheral hospitals

Figure 2: Role of FAST scan in trauma cases

LITERATURE REVIEW

J.M. Artigas Martín et al.,2015 studied that the The data gathered from the trauma scene can offer hints about the potential mechanism and pattern of injuries, it is subjective and not a very sensitive indicator of significant injury.⁸

John R. Richards et al.,2017 studied that the FAST (Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma) test has a sensitivity of roughly 63% for detecting solid organ damage, but a moderate to high sensitivity (varying from 69% to 98%) for identifying free fluid. Because of this, it might understate the severity or existence of injuries, especially in trauma patients who are hemodynamically stable and do not exhibit any free fluid.⁹

IM Smith et al.,2015 study came to the conclusion that both CT scans and FAST (Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma) are essential for assessing abdominal trauma sustained on the battlefield.FAST was emphasized as being useful for quick triage, particularly in situations with limited resources or during battle.For surgical decision-making, CT imaging was more conclusive, highlighting the need to use both methods in tandem whenever feasible.¹⁰

Bala Bala Natarajan MBBS et al.,2010 state that Our institute assessed 2,980 trauma cases during a seven-year period. A Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) was performed on 2,130 of them. Seven patients were declared dead upon arrival, while 18 cases had inconclusive FAST results. 2,105 patients were then available for examination. Using the FAST assessment, 88 of these instances were determined to be true positives.¹¹

Khadija Hussain et al.,2021 studied that the nine of the 20 chosen studies concentrated on CT scans and six explored the ultrasonography uses. The combined use of CT and MRI was examined in one study. Imaging techniques for cases of polytrauma were the subject of two research. The last two

studies looked at imaging procedures and diagnostic errors in trauma care settings with limited resources.⁴

Kadir Agladioglu et al.,2016 says that the mean age of the 447 patients under analysis was 39.5 ± 19.2 years, with 309 (69.1%) being male and ranging in age from 9 to 87 years. 158 patients (35.3%) were injured in motor vehicle accidents. With a 95% CI of 78.3% (63.6–89), chest X-rays (CXR) showed the maximum sensitivity for detecting clavicle fractures. With a 95% CI of 11.8% (1.5–36.4), its sensitivity for identifying pneumomediastinum was noticeably lower. In spite of this, CXR demonstrated almost flawless specificity in a wide range of circumstances.¹²

A Oikonomou et al.,2011 studied about patient injury and state that When it comes to identifying chest injuries, CT is generally acknowledged to be more accurate than chest X-rays. Furthermore, trauma patients can now receive critical treatment more quickly because to the development of multidetector CT (MDCT), which has significantly reduced imaging times for these patients to only a few seconds.¹³

K Ziegler et al.,2013 stated that the analysis included 239 individuals who had thoracic CT (TCT) and chest X-rays (CXR) performed between January 1 and December 31, 2010, and who satisfied both inclusion and exclusion criteria. CXR was found to have a specificity of 91.7% (95% CI: 86.7%–95%) and a sensitivity of 19% (95% CI: 10.8%–31%). False negative rates were 24.5% (95% CI: 18.8%–31.2%) and false positive rates were 35.8% (95% CI: 21.7%–52.8%). The test's overall diagnostic accuracy was 74.1% (95% CI: 68.1%–79.2%), while its precision was estimated to be 42.3% (95% CI: 25.5%–61.1%).¹⁴

STUDY	COUNTRY	OBJECTIVE	FINDINGS
1. M. Omraninava et al.,2023	Iran	To evaluate how effective FAST (Focused Assessment with Sonography in Trauma) is in identifying blunt abdominal injuries in trauma patients.	The study came to the conclusion that both CT scans and FAST (Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma) are essential for assessing abdominal trauma sustained on the battlefield. FAST was emphasized as being useful for quick triage, particularly in situations with limited resources or during battle. For surgical decision-making, CT imaging was more conclusive, highlighting the need to use both methods in tandem whenever

			feasible.
2.Sorravit savatmongkorngul et al., 2017	Thailand	To provide an overview of the use and significance of FAST in trauma diagnosis and its application in emergency settings.	The article examines the use of Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) in a range of contexts, such as pediatric patients, emergency rooms, and prehospital treatment. FAST plays a very important part in detecting free fluid in trauma patients, which facilitates quick decisions during resuscitation. The authors stress the importance of FAST in contemporary trauma care while going over its advantages, drawbacks, and implementation difficulties.
3. Yasmin Z. Attia et al.,2023	Egypt	To compare the efficacy of the NEXUS chest algorithm and extended FAST (E-FAST) in identifying blunt chest trauma in patients with multiple injuries.	When it comes to detecting hemothorax, pneumothorax, and chest injuries, E-FAST has a higher specificity than the NEXUS chest algorithm, which had the lowest specificity. To successfully rule out thoracic injury, the NEXUS chest algorithm, on the other hand, demonstrated a higher sensitivity than E-FAST.
4. Khadija Hussain et	USA and UK	To discuss the crucial	While eFAST and X-

al.,2021		role of radiologists in trauma care and the integration of radiology into trauma management systems.	rays are commonly used first in trauma cases, CT imaging remains the most sensitive and should be employed when the patient's history and examination indicates the need.
5. Pierre Bouzat et al.,2020	France	To explore early intervention approaches for managing severe abdominal injuries in critical care environments.	The goal of the study was to create French management guidelines for patients who have suffered serious abdominal damage. These rules were developed by a consensus committee including 20 specialists from different French medical societies and institutions. The guidelines include early surveillance for severe abdominal trauma, therapeutic options, and diagnostic techniques. The GRADE approach was used to create recommendations, yielding 15 statements: four based on expert judgment, six with low-level evidence, and five with high-level evidence. In order to lower morbidity and mortality in patients with severe abdominal trauma, the study highlights the significance of early

			and correct diagnosis, adequate surgical intervention, and efficient monitoring.
6. Essa Ibrahim H.Shaeri et al.,2024	Saudia Arabia	To assess the role of radiologic techniques in identifying and managing injuries resulting from trauma.	Clinical judgments and results are greatly impacted by radiological imaging, which is essential for the diagnosis and treatment of trauma patients. Methods including MRIs, CT scans, and X-rays offer comprehensive information on injuries, enabling timely and precise diagnosis. Improved patient care and resource allocation have resulted from improvements in imaging technology's ability to detect subtle injuries. Notwithstanding the advantages, issues with radiation exposure, expense, and possible over-reliance on imaging are mentioned. In order to maximize patient care, the study promotes a well-rounded strategy that combines imaging and clinical assessments.
7. Josephine Valenzuela et al.,2020	USA	To investigate how incidental findings are recorded and communicated during FAST examinations in	A retrospective analysis of 1,452 FAST tests conducted in EDs revealed that 137 patients (9.4%) had

		trauma cases.	incidental results. In women, pelvic cysts (22.2%) and renal cysts (34%), incidental observations were most prevalent. Just 4.4% of patients were reported to have been told of their incidental findings, and only 21.5% of these results were recorded in ultrasonography reports or medical records by emergency department doctors.
8. J.M. Artigas Martín et al.,2015	Spain	To provide a comprehensive review of imaging techniques used to assess severe trauma, with a focus on radiology's role.	The information obtained from the trauma scene is subjective and not a very sensitive indicator of serious damage, It can offer insights into the likely cause and nature of the injuries.
9. John R. Richards et al.,2017	USA	To explore how the practice of FAST has evolved and what it means for radiologists working in trauma care.	The FAST (Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma) test has a sensitivity of around 63% for detecting solid organ injury, but a moderate to high sensitivity (ranging from 69% to 98%) for identifying free fluid. Because of this, it could understate the degree or occurrence of injuries, especially in trauma patients who are hemodynamically stable and do not

			demonstrate any free fluid.
10. IM Smith et al.,2015	United Kingdom	To examine the utility and effectiveness of FAST and CT scans for assessing abdominal injuries on the battlefield.	The research assessed how well computed tomography (CT) and FAST ultrasound detect abdominal injuries in combat patients treated at the Role 3 Medical Treatment Facility in Camp Bastion, Afghanistan.
11.Bala Bala Natarajan MBBS et al.,2010	USA	To evaluate the benefits of FAST scans for stable blunt trauma patients showing minimal signs of injury.	Our institute reviewed 2,980 trauma cases over a seven-year period. 2,130 of them underwent a Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST). Eighteen cases had inconclusive FAST findings, and seven patients were pronounced dead upon arrival. At that time, 2,105 patients could be examined. Eighty-eight of these cases were identified as true positives using the FAST evaluation.
12.Kadir Agladioglu et al.,2016	Turkey	To measure the effectiveness of chest X-rays in identifying injuries resulting from blunt trauma.	Of the 447 patients analyzed, 309 (69.1%) were male and ranged in age from 9 to 87 years, with a mean age of 39.5 ± 19.2 years. A total of 158 patients (35.3%) suffered

			<p>injuries in auto accidents. Chest X-rays (CXR) demonstrated the highest sensitivity for detecting clavicle fractures, with a 95% confidence interval (CI) of 78.3% (63.6–89). Its sensitivity for detecting pneumomediastinum was significantly lower, with a 95% CI of 11.8% (1.5–36.4). Despite this, CXR showed nearly perfect specificity under a variety of conditions.</p>
13. A Oikonomou et al.,2011	Greece	To assess the function of CT scans in diagnosing blunt chest trauma and its clinical relevance.	<p>CT is widely accepted as being more accurate than chest X-rays in detecting chest ailments. Additionally, the invention of multidetector CT (MDCT) has greatly shortened imaging periods for trauma patients to only a few seconds, allowing them to obtain essential treatment more swiftly.</p>
14. K Ziegler et al.,2013	USA	To evaluate the practicality and cost-effectiveness of routine chest X-rays in trauma care protocols.	<p>A total of 239 individuals who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria and underwent thoracic CT (TCT) and chest X-rays (CXR) from January 1 to December 31, 2010, were analyzed. The</p>

			<p>results showed that CXR had a sensitivity of 19% (95% CI: 10.8%–31%) and a specificity of 91.7% (95% CI: 86.7%–95%). The rates of false positives were 35.8% (95% CI: 21.7%–52.8%) and false negatives were 24.5% (95% CI: 18.8%–31.2%). The test's precision was estimated to be 42.3% (95% CI: 25.5%–61.1%), and its overall diagnostic accuracy was 74.1% (95% CI: 68.1%–79.2%).</p>
15. Savoia P. et al, 2023.	Brazil	To discuss how the FAST examination is utilized in modern trauma diagnosis using ultrasound technology.	<p>The Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) procedure is thoroughly described in the article, with a focus on its usage as a quick, noninvasive, bedside ultrasound method for trauma patient evaluation. Hemodynamically unstable patients with blunt abdominal trauma, penetrating injuries at the thoracoabdominal transition, or unexplained hypotension are the main candidates for FAST. Four locations are examined by the</p>

			conventional FAST protocol: the pelvis (for hemoperitoneum), right upper quadrant, left upper quadrant, and pericardium (for cardiac tamponade).
16. Benjamin A et al.,2019	USA	To summarize the application of FAST exams in trauma care and its benefits in emergency medical settings.	The Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) technique is thoroughly described in the article, with special attention to its function as a quick, noninvasive bedside ultrasound examination that finds free fluid in trauma patients' peritoneal, pericardial, and pleural regions.
17. Bella F M et al., 2025	Italy	To provide a thorough review of the extended FAST technique in the context of emergency department trauma management.	When evaluating trauma patients in the emergency department (ED), the Extended Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (eFAST) is a quick, non-invasive bedside ultrasound method that is essential. By incorporating evaluations for hemothorax and pneumothorax, eFAST improves on the conventional FAST examination and enables the early

			detection of potentially fatal diseases such hemoperitoneum, hemothorax, and cardiac tamponade.
18. Najeeb Ullah et al.,2022	Pakistan	To investigate the accuracy and dependability of FAST for diagnosing blunt torso trauma in emergency settings.	To assess the accuracy of Focused Assessment with Sonography for injuries (FAST) in identifying blunt torso injuries, the study performed a meta-analysis. The qualitative synthesis comprised 46 published papers in total. According to the results, FAST can diagnose blunt abdominal trauma with good sensitivity and specificity. However, the fact that different studies have different sensitivity and specificity indicates that the expertise, technique, and equipment employed by the operator all affect how successful FAST is.
19. Kim P K et al.,2017	USA	To explore the role of radiology in trauma management, especially in surgical practice and decision-making.	The importance of imaging modalities in the assessment and treatment of trauma victims is emphasized in this review study. The combination of a chest radiograph, a pelvic radiograph, and Focused Assessment

			with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) or extended FAST (eFAST) is advised for quick torso evaluation of hemodynamically unstable or borderline patients. In cases of blunt trauma, computed tomography (CT) has emerged as the gold standard for conclusive imaging. When evaluating potential vascular injuries in the neck and limbs, CT angiography is especially helpful. Concerns about the population-level cumulative radiation exposure from CT scans are also raised in the article.
20. Locabellis F et al ,. 2022	Italy	To review current standards in emergency radiology and its impact on the care of critically injured trauma patients.	In developed nations, high-energy trauma is a major cause of death and disability for people under 35, with bleeding and brain injuries accounting for the majority of fatalities. The care of significant traumas has changed due to advancements in imaging techniques, especially computed tomography (CT), which has replaced traditional surgical assessments with more

			<p>accurate imaging-based evaluations. Depending on CT data and the radiologist's skill, interventional radiology (IR) has become a crucial nonoperative therapy option for vascular lesions brought on by physical trauma. As essential members of the trauma team, emergency and IR radiologists have helped develop specialized management plans that have significantly decreased morbidity and death.</p>
21. Alexander Backer et al.,2010	Israel	To assess the reliability of the FAST examination in patients with severe trauma and multiple injuries.	Compared to patients with lower or intermediate Injury Severity Scores (ISS), individuals with higher ISS levels are more likely to have injuries that ultrasound cannot detect, which lowers the diagnostic accuracy.
22. Jane Smith et al.,2010	UK	To reevaluate the role of FAST in trauma diagnostics and consider whether its clinical use should be reassessed.	The importance of the Focused Assessment with Sonography in Trauma (FAST) in the assessment of patients with blunt abdominal trauma is critically examined in this paper. Despite FAST's

			widespread use due to its quick bedside evaluation capabilities, the article points out a number of drawbacks.
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DISCUSSION

Trauma-related injuries are a significant global health issue, with the World Health Organization estimating nearly 14,000 deaths each day—approximately one death every six seconds. These injuries represent the most common cause of death in individuals between the ages of one and forty-five. This trend is largely driven by the expansion of transportation systems and population growth, which have contributed to the increasing incidence of physical trauma in recent years. Among various causes, traffic accidents are the leading contributor to trauma, followed by falls, drowning, burns, sports injuries, interpersonal violence, and conflict-related injuries.⁴

Thoracic trauma alone accounts for over five million cases annually, resulting in more than 500,000 surgical interventions and over 50,000 fatalities. On average, trauma-related deaths cause a loss of 40 years of life and 18 years of potential productivity. Abdominal trauma is present in approximately 7% to 10% of all trauma cases, with nearly a quarter of these requiring surgical management. Most abdominal injuries—up to 85%—are the result of blunt force trauma, which poses diagnostic and treatment challenges in acute care settings.¹⁵

Early detection of trauma-related injuries is essential in minimizing both mortality and long-term disability. A prompt and accurate assessment is particularly important for patients who are hemodynamically unstable or only partially stable. Initial evaluation often involves the use of plain radiographs, ultrasound, and computed tomography (CT) scans. A typical first-line diagnostic approach includes a chest X-ray, pelvic X-ray, and a Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) or its extended version (eFAST). Relying solely on a patient's history and physical examination can often result in missed diagnoses, especially in high-stakes trauma settings. Research indicates that without the use of medical imaging, between 20% and 50% of blunt trauma cases may be misdiagnosed.¹⁶

The FAST and eFAST protocols are widely used in emergency settings for the rapid detection of internal bleeding, particularly in the pericardial, pleural, and abdominal cavities. These are mainly used for the identification of hemopericardium, hemopneumothorax, and hemoperitoneum.¹⁷

In trauma settings, the discovery of any fluid is generally presumed to be blood until proven otherwise. However, ultrasound technology cannot distinguish between types of fluid, which may result in false positives in patients with conditions such as ascites, pleural effusion, ruptured ovarian cysts, bladder

rupture, or those undergoing peritoneal dialysis. On the other hand, false negatives may occur when bleeding is confined to areas not covered by standard FAST views or when imaging is compromised by factors such as obesity, subcutaneous emphysema, or poor acoustic windows.¹⁸

The integration of FAST into trauma protocols like the Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS) system, which is implemented in over 60 countries, highlights its established role in emergency medicine. The ATLS framework emphasizes the importance of early imaging in the initial stages of trauma care, typically during the so-called “golden hour” following injury. This critical period demands rapid clinical assessments and decisions to improve survival chances. The protocol usually includes cervical spine, chest, and pelvic X-rays, as well as FAST and CT scans when appropriate. FAST is especially well-suited to this model as it allows for the rapid identification of life-threatening conditions, helps guide immediate interventions, and facilitates monitoring through repeat evaluations.¹⁹

CT remains the gold standard for evaluating injuries to the head, abdomen, spine, pelvis, and facial structures. In cases of head trauma, CT allows for prompt identification of intracranial bleeding, fractures, and swelling, which is critical for determining the need for surgical intervention. CT can help in finalizing nonoperative treatments for patients those are hemodynamically stable with serious organ injuries.⁸

Despite its advantages, CT scanning has limitations, particularly in patients who are too unstable to be safely transported to the radiology suite. In such scenarios, bedside imaging using FAST and eFAST offers an immediate and life-saving alternative. This bedside capability allows for the continuation of resuscitative efforts without delay, improving outcomes in critically ill patients.²⁰

FAST is particularly effective in detecting thoracic injuries. It has demonstrated a high positive predictive value for identifying conditions such as pericardial effusion, cardiac tamponade, and pneumothorax. In blunt abdominal trauma cases, a positive FAST result generally leads to follow-up CT imaging to confirm findings and provide detailed localization. Although ultrasound may not replace CT in terms of diagnostic detail, it plays a vital role in initial triage and decision-making, especially in resource-limited settings or when patient instability prohibits transport.²¹

To ensure optimal use of FAST, healthcare professionals—particularly emergency physicians and trauma surgeons—should receive specialized training. Incorporating FAST into all phases of trauma management—preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative—further strengthens its role in modern trauma care. With its speed, repeatability, and non-invasive nature, FAST supports life-saving decisions and enhances the overall efficiency of trauma response protocols.²²

Hence, Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma is an indispensable tool in the early evaluation and management of trauma patients. Its ability to

identify internal bleeding and organ injury quickly makes it essential for rapid decision-making and triage.

CONCLUSION

FAST examination is pivotal non-invasive and expeditious tool for inceptive assessment of trauma patients. The promptness in identification of potential anatomical alterations caused by trauma, with the help of FAST radiological examination, helps in rapid and accurate diagnosis of life-threatening injuries, crucial clinical decision making, reduce diagnostic delays and keep the track of progress and deteriorations. FAST comprehensively enhances the quality of trauma-focused care.

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